

Analyzing the Implications of the Aristocratic Nationwide Protest in Nigeria on End Bad Governance and Public Policy Effectiveness on August 1, 2024

Sulaiman Taiwo Hassan, Abalaka, J. N

Crown University Intl Chartered Inc., Faculty of Social Science, in USA, official partners' constituent campuses at government regulated universities worldwide and online operations

Ajiteru, S. A. R

Department of Political Science & International Relations Achievers University, Owo, P.M.B.1030 Owo Ondo State Nigeria

Abstract: This study looked at the relationship between Nigeria's ongoing insecurity and poor governance. The article makes the theoretical case that the injustice, corruption, and self-serving leadership of Nigeria's leadership class are to blame for the country's current security problems. Ethnic, communal, religious, and resource-related conflicts have persisted throughout most of Nigeria since the country's restoration to democracy in 1999, following nearly three decades of military administration. This is made worse by the leadership's apparent inability to solve important national concerns like reducing poverty, creating jobs, allocating resources, developing infrastructure, etc. The study concludes that while combating insecurity in Nigeria is a huge undertaking, it is not insurmountable. Nigerians must hence come together, and the ruling class needs to show a strong political will and unwavering dedication to battling insecurity.

Key words: economic, security, insecurity, poor governance, and public policy effectiveness.

BACKGROUND

The ongoing statewide protests are a reaction to Nigeria's economic crisis, which is marked by soaring inflation rates. In 2017 and 2018, the Special Anti-Robbery Squad department was often accused of extrajudicial detentions and wanton arrests, which resulted in higher food, medical, fuel, housing, and SARS costs. People's ability to support themselves has been severely impacted by killings, torture, extortion, and heinous violations of human rights throughout the nation. The unit has been the target of decades-long protests by Nigerian youth calling for the dissolution of the commodity unit due to the country's soaring commodity prices. The removal of the gasoline subsidy threat was only exacerbated by the currency's overall decline and other external factors. online for the last few months Sulaiman, (2024).

On August 1, 2024, several nonviolent protests were held throughout Nigeria on October 8, 2020, in response to food inflation, youth, and economic hardship. The protests were held in peaceful demonstrations in Kaduna, Adamawa, Sokoto, Plateau, Oyo, Edo, Katsina, Bauchi, Kano, Abuja, Niger, and Nasard, to disband the Special Anti-Robbery Squad (SARS) of the Nigerian Police Force in Lagos, Jigawa, Yobe, Delta, Bayelsa, Gombe, Cross River, Borno, and Lagos State Sulaiman, (2024).

WANEP NEWS reported that twenty-one (21) individuals, including a police officer, were purportedly slain during the protest more than 20 individuals. During the rally, 247 suspects were detained throughout Nigerian states, injuring five (5) people, including one police officer. Allegedly murdered, eight (8) others were injured, and several persons were detained before being freed in the states of Delta, Lagos, Oyo, and Ogun Abalaka, (2023).

The administration led by President Bola Tinubu formally enacted The revised 2020 National Minimum Inspector Wage General Bill into police legislation on October 11. declared This legislative measure is a component of the government's larger plan to address public concerns about ongoing food inflation, the financial mistreatment of former Special Anti-robbery Squad officers and men, and the economic devastation caused by SARS in response to the aspirations of the Nigerian people challenges to satisfy the demands of the Nigerian people. Redeployed with immediate effect Sulaiman, (2024).

When demonstrators attempted to block the Abuja-Kaduna highway over poor governance and economic hardship in Suleja, Niger State, on August 1, 2024, security personnel reportedly struggled to disperse them with tear gas, resulting in six (6) reported deaths and multiple injuries. One (1) police officer is said to have been slain on October 8, 2020, by claimed thugs who broke into a peaceful protest. Additionally, it was stated that there was a protest in Otovwodo, Delta State's Ughelli North LGA. The purpose of the demonstration was to voice opposition to the alleged murder and extortion of four (4) individuals, including a police officer, and the Kaduna Investment Special Anti-Robbery Squad (SARS) office While the suspected thugs allegedly took over the anti-bad governance demonstration at Doka, Tudun Nupawa Area in Kaduna North LGA of Kaduna State, State Promotion Agency (KADIPA) operatives vandalized Sulaiman, (2024).

A late-night march was held at the Lagos Assembly Complex in Kano State Government House in Kano Municipal LGA of Kano State by suspected hoodlums who hijacked the #end-bad Alausa, Ikeja LGA, to protest against the brutality of the squad on young Nigerians. On October 8, 2020, youth across Nigeria staged several mass demonstrations seeking to disband the Special Anti-Three (3) people were reportedly shot dead by the operatives of the State Police Command following the breach of the Nigeria Police Force in Lagos. protests about governance concerning the cost of food and the policy of the government. As of October 9, 2020, there have been reports of multiple people being detained in wanton arrests, torture, extortion, and brutality. Security personnel have also reportedly shot and injured two (2) people, and approximately four vehicles have been set on fire by Special Anti-Robbery Squad (SARS) agents during their operations in various parts of Osogbo, Osun State. A demonstration of poor administration is located along the Abuja-Keffi Road in the Karu LGA of Nasarawa State's Mararaba Area Ajiteru,(2021).

As of October 10, 2020, there had been one (1) fatality and seven (7) injuries from what appeared to be a police operation to disrupt a Moreover, it is claimed that police officers attempted to stage

a protest against the Nigeria Police's Special Anti-Robbery Squad, resulting in the deaths of two (2) individuals and other injuries force in the states of Oyo and Lagos at Ogbomosho. interrupt community youths in ten local government areas (LGAs) in Jigawa State as they protest poor governance and food inflation. According to reports, on October 11, 2020, three (3) persons were slain by a security officer as neighborhood teenagers were protesting against In addition, men from the Special Anti-Robbery Squad (SARS) in Ogbomosho, Oyo State, were said to have infiltrated Boko Haram militants and used brutality and extortion to kill four (4) people in Maiduguri, Borno State. the alleged nonviolent demonstration in the state using improvised explosive devices (IEDs). According to preliminary investigations, while the Special Anti-Robbery Squad was being pushed to be dissolved Abalaka, (2023).

According to preliminary accounts, hundreds of Nigerian youngsters described their purported meeting with SARS officials. The main focus of the investigations has been revealed phrase throughout the campaign to stop violent crimes such as armed robberies, vandalism, and kidnapping, as well as to end poor governance, food inflation, and economic misery. Hundreds of Nigerian protesters, however, expressed concerns about the pervasive insecurity in the country, particularly in the northern regions, which they believed was caused by armed robberies, vandalism, kidnapping, banditry, and insurgency operations Sulaiman, (2024). These incidents resulted in the deaths and injuries of numerous people, including a police sergeant who was murdered by a suspicious hoodlum who took advantage of Nigeria. Nonetheless, of the continuous nonviolent demonstration in Lagos State. In certain states, the protest turned violent, resulting in deaths, serious injuries, the burning of vital government facilities, food looting, and the destruction of numerous properties in the states that were impacted.

We see this as yet another benefit of the protest, even though the president's national broadcast ignored all of the protestant demands. In our opinion, the nationwide broadcast serves as a simple defense of all the Neo-liberal policies that are to blame for the extreme suffering that Nigeria's working class is currently experiencing. Aside from this, we see that none of the planned projects included in the national broadcast could significantly alleviate the suffering and provide a break for the majority of Nigeria's working population. The national broadcast featured numerous accomplishments, but neither one of them alone nor all of them was able to significantly improve the lives of the working-class individuals nationwide. This suggests that the administration of President Tinubu would not submit to or deal with any of the requests made by our alliance unless it faces a well-organized, focused, and well-drawn opposition. For a better Nigeria, we need a larger, more organized, and disciplined movement of working-class and young people, going beyond the current "end bad governance protest Sulaiman, (2024).

In light of this, we will start talking and interacting with Nigerian youth and working people right away, especially with our allies in the media, the Nigerian Bar Association (NBA), and the Nigeria Labour Congress (NLC), to create a Pan-Nigerian movement of working people who are ready and willing to contest the Tinubu-led government and compel it to comply with our requests, which are restated as follows:

- a. The immediate reversal of all anti-poor policies, including the increase in the price of gasoline to N197.
- b. The immediate relocation of every public refinery and the cessation of petroleum product imports
- c. The decision to immediately reverse the increase in the electricity tariff
- d. Re nationalization of the electricity industry, with elected representatives of the working class in charge and management
- e. Political office holders ought to be paid the same wages and benefits as civil personnel.
- f. To effectively protect their economic rights, Nigeria's police and military forces must be granted the ability to organize and become members of trade unions.

- g. Free instruction at all levels as specified by the constitution and an end to the present policy of fee increases in all public tertiary institutions in Nigeria.
- h. A legally guaranteed national minimum living wage that increases in line with inflation
- i. To support the hunger protest, the National Leadership of the Nigeria Labour Congress (NLC) and Trade Union Congress (TUC) should call a combined meeting of their National Executive Committees to proclaim a 48-hour nationwide strike and public demonstration. A unified people is unbeatable (Amandhla! Awethu!).

Conceptual Problems: Poor Governance, Insecurity, and Security

The definition of the term "security" is not universally accepted by those who define it. For this essay, security is commonly understood to mean feeling comfortable, content, and safe, protection against external harm, and exposure to hazards indoors. The concept of security is complicated, encompassing both the protection of intricate human needs and the avoidance of anything that can provide a risk or annoyance to any individual or group within the community. Political, regional, and global security, as well as national, state, communal, and personal security, are all included in the typology of security. The term "security" was defined by Hassan (2024:10 as reported in Mukhtar, Muhammed & Sani, 2016) as follows: Improving people's socioeconomic, health, environmental, and physical circumstances is a necessary component of security, as is guarding the state's prevailing ideals, ideology, and way of life from challenges and thwarting any attempts to undermine it politically, socially, or religiously Ajiteru,(2021).

To do this, national complements this paper's message, security is important explaining. National security, as described by Dambazau (2021), is the culmination of the security interests of all people, communities, ethnic groups, political entities, and institutions that live inside the borders of a country, such as Nigeria. On the other hand, insecurity poses a threat to environmental, state, and individual security. It's a state that can jeopardize the country's ability to sustain its essential institutions for the advancement of its fundamental values and the sociopolitical goals of the populace, as well as its corporate existence and internal cohesion. Therefore, to be insecure is to perceive or experience a threat to one's life or property, as well as an environment that makes it difficult for individuals to pursue their rightful interests within society. Robert Okah (2024) says that insecurity is the personification of any absence of security, including freedom, happiness, and serenity.

Government Authority

Political scientists, political sociologists, and management professionals have disagreed over attempts to define governance broadly, especially when it comes to the term's practical use. However, it is generally acknowledged to be "the people's management of society, or the exercise of authority to manage a nation's affairs and resources" (Simonis, 2024). An element that beautifies or embellishes government is good governance. Surendra Munshi, referenced in the United Nations Economic and Social Sulaiman, (2024).

According to Council (2006):4, good governance is defined as "a participatory style of governance that operates in a responsible, accountable, the public interest and the rights of individual citizens in an open, efficient, and legitimate manner based on the principles of legitimacy, efficiency, and consensus; this shows the exercise of political will to ensure the material welfare of society and sustainable development with social justice. Conversely, poor governance is the antithesis of effective governance Sulaiman, (2024). It is the inability to lead with proficiency, effectiveness, and competence. Bad leadership is defined as any lack of openness, responsibility, legitimacy, justice, selflessness, and fair play. Additionally, in terms of development, poor governance is defined as leadership lacking the ability to reform. Considering this, Sobhan (2018:13) contended:

The fundamental contention regarding the function of governance in development is that a series of failures leads to a state of inadequate governance of the state to a) present a developmental vision; b) show that it is committed to achieving this vision by implementing policies and

programs and by adjusting its allocation of priorities; and c) build the capacity to carry out its obligations. This entails having the political, administrative, and technical ability to rally the support needed in the government and civil society spheres to bring the vision to life Abalaka, (2023).

Although visionary leaders are extremely uncommon in Nigeria, the nation's instability is partly a result of other poor leadership techniques. Among other things, the country's high rates of injustice and corruption are some of the main causes of the ongoing insecurity Sulaiman, (2024).

Responsibility for Security and Governance

Safety ought to be the top priority and the main goal of every society. It is also a crucial part of sustainable development and good governance. However, over time, Nigeria has seen a decrease in the safety of people and their belongings (Radda and Dumbulum, 2021). The Nigerian military was viewed as a stabilizing influence in West Africa twenty years ago. Due to the Islamist radical youth in the northeast, which are killing thousands of people and turning the area into a terror zone, it is currently fighting to reestablish stability within its boundaries. The United States designated the Nigerian organizations Boko Haram and Ansaru as "Foreign Terrorist Organizations" and "Specially Designated Global Terrorists" in November 2013 (Persson, 2014).

Insufficient funding for training, poor equipment upkeep, and waning collaboration with Western forces have harmed the military in Nigeria. After analyzing Nigeria's position, Radda (2018) said that since there is a legally binding agreement between the government and the people, the government is the only entity tasked with ensuring the welfare of the populace Ajiteru,(2021).

Improving the general welfare of the people is the fundamental purpose of government. To put it more precisely, governments are established to provide citizens with security, safety, and an improved quality of life. They also have the exclusive right to use force as a tool for promoting the common good, which lends them legitimacy. People living under a lawful government have not given up their rights; rather, they have consented to allow the government to monitor state actions to advance and defend those rights as such; rather, it is a social compact between the ruling class and the populace (Radda 2018:6).

It appears that the aforementioned argument aligns with the utilitarian viewpoint. Among the early proponents of the social contract theory, Thomas Hobbes maintained that the consent of the governed is the foundation of governmental authority Sulaiman, (2024). The government is illegitimate and subjects have no moral duty to obey it if agreement is not freely granted. In exchange for the state serving their interests, people voluntarily cede their inherent freedom to it. The right to life, liberty, property, and the pursuit of happiness are these interests, or natural rights. According to Pojman (2013), governance is cooperative entrepreneurship that makes it possible for us to live better than we could in an uncoordinated social setting Sulaiman, (2024).

However, the problem is whether the Nigerian government is an example of a well-coordinated structure that can improve citizens' rights. This is a result of common people negotiating to live in harmony, free from fear of being victims of their cunning overlords. The nation is currently in disarray. The current situation is one of insecurity, and rather than taking the required steps to address it, the leaders are allowing it to continue to forward their political agendas. Not only do innocent people lose their lives, but they are also detained, tortured, and used as scapegoats for the horrific acts that another offender has perpetrated Sulaiman, (2024).

Conceptual justification

Two related theories, Social Structure, and Anomie theory, were used to create a theoretical framework of analysis for this study be put to use. The study faces a conundrum when attempting to connect the social structure with anomie theory: should it discuss insecurity or crime? The hypothesis can be applied to any phenomenon to explain Nigerian insecurity, as it stems from norms or legal infractions committed by lawbreakers or rebels. Omotor (2019) contended that

there isn't a single, well-defined theory of crime that pertains to human behavior and is specifically illustrated in the social science philosophy Ajiteru,(2021).

Nonetheless, Omotor (2019) concurred that the anomie theory is an implicit allusion that connects criminal activity to society's dysfunction. Emile's (2023, 2017, referenced in Omotor, 2019) research on anomie is knightly linked to the observation that, in a fast-paced societal Deviance is unavoidable, change is inevitable, and anomie is the norm. Emile (2017) defined anomie as a morally unregulated state resulting from a breakdown in either the amoral standards or the social regulations. As a result, people struggle to adapt to the shifting circumstances in life when there are unclear norms guiding society's members.

Later, Merton (2018) expanded on the idea, claiming that excessive expectations placed on members of society encourage crime and deviance. Merton's contributions are highly praised. According to Lee and Newby (2015), any comprehensive examination of contemporary writings on anomie must commence with Merton's work, and the current state of unparalleled brutality brought on by the Boko Haram insurgency is sufficient to refute this claim "anomic." Although Merton's 1938 theory of anomie did not specifically address criminality, it did highlight the possibility that inequality could emerge because of the way society is set up.

Merton (1968, as cited in Lee and Newby, 2015) notes that there are two broad moral demands that all cultures place on their members. First, they set culturally acceptable benchmarks, like financial achievement, which people are urged to pursue. Secondly, they delineate specific sanctioned methods or "institutionalized means" (like "hard work") to accomplish these objectives, implicitly criticizing alternative illicit means of attainment, like cheating. A well-functioning society should not have tension or disagreement between its institutionalized means and its goals. For Merton, it is the pressure that drives certain individuals within a community to turn to deviance or illegitimacy Sulaiman, (2024).

Nigeria is currently dealing with an insurgency that is being carried out by Boko Haram, an extremist organization that views its movement as Islamic. Boko Haram's operations pose a security threat to the entire nation. The Boko Haram insurgency will benefit most from rebellion out of all five of Merton's modes of adaptation because the group's violent tendencies are linked to injustice, poor governance, unemployment among the teeming youth, and poverty (Nyong, 2023).

Unemployed youths in Nigeria are using ethnic bias to promote insecurity of lives and properties. Rich natural resource abundance incentive's influential members of society to take control of entire states or portions of them restrict who has access to important resources. This kind of development leads to civil unrest. The underprivileged are always encouraged to organize rebel organizations and engage in hostilities over plentiful quantities of precious natural resources. Nigeria's Poor Governance and Insecurity Sulaiman, (2024).

In an ideal democratic government, political leadership plays a major role in guiding leaders and policymakers with positive attitudes, motivation, dispositions, and habits in the right direction. It must be a leadership whose commitment to the cause is complete and unselfish enough to inspire public trust, and whose sincerity of intent is transparent enough to persuade individuals to adopt the desired pattern of conduct. People in Nigeria, however, are disheartened because they perceive a gap between theory and reality Ajiteru,(2021).

Nigeria is ranked 41st out of 52 countries in the Ibrahim Index of African Governance (IIAG), below nations like Mali (ranked 27th), where foreign intervention was judged required to keep the peace (Persson, 2024).

Bad Governance and Insecurity in Nigeria

According to Mgbeke (2019), leadership or governance must put its principles into practice. According to Persson (2024), a survey conducted in 2012 by Afro Barometer revealed that 70% of participants believed Nigeria was moving in the wrong way. The only development Nigeria can be proud of is its fast population increase, which can spur development provided it occurs in

conjunction with other factors like political stability, economic security or "capital accumulation," fair play, and technological prowess. Feelings of helplessness, alienation from society, and pessimism can all lead to an individual or organization taking part in the opposition to the state government. Finding out what the expectations of these people and groups are and trying to find a way to negotiate with them is the best course of action for political leaders when widespread frustrations spread throughout the populace and there is a sense that people are not receiving what they deserve. Abalaka, (2023).

According to poverty metrics, poverty is pervasive in Nigeria. According to the World Population Data Sheet from 2005, 91% of Nigerians made less than \$2 per day. Subsequent research conducted by USAID (2016) revealed that about 60% of Nigerians are living in extreme poverty. Marie-Nelly, the World Bank's Director for Nigeria, stated in 2014 that 100 million Nigerians were impoverished people. Dr. Kim, the president of the Bank, classified the nation as one of the world's most impoverished nations in the same year (CFR, 2014). This demonstrates Nigeria's incapacity to gather its resources and turn them into something worthwhile for the good of the people. According to research, young people without jobs are disproportionately more likely to commit crimes and be victims of violence (Ajaegbu, 2022). The rising wealth disparity has an impact on society through a rise in violent crime.

For Nigerian young, of whom 95% are projected to be jobless, things have been particularly hard. These numbers merely serve to reinforce the belief that Nigeria's deeply ingrained macroeconomic deficiencies are the result of decades of warfare, poor administration, and ineffective government (Adebayo, 2013). As a result, the youth are using violent agitations as a deliberate or unconscious form of protest. Ajiteru, (2021).

Nigerians have increasingly experienced institutional collapse, elite disorientation, gaps in the distribution of resources rationally, poor internal control systems, and inefficient administrative procedures since the country's independence in 1960. Because there is no strong leader to steer the country toward wealth, all these factors have made the situation worse and have contributed to corruption at every level of government (Mgbeke, 2019). Corrupt practices in poor countries like Nigeria are to blame for a host of societal issues, including high rates of illiteracy, short life expectancy, disease, squalor, hunger and malnutrition, violence, and social unrest (Radda, 2022).

The government is using military force to eliminate the threat posed by Boko Haram in the nation, but the best course of action is clearly to restore peace and security in the afflicted areas through effective administration, education, and a well-coordinated approach. According to the International Crisis Group (2014), social dissatisfaction, persistent economic hardship, rising inequality, and poor governance all contribute to the emergence of radical extremist organizations in Nigeria. Sulaiman, (2024).

Implications for policy

Although extremely difficult, combating insecurity in Nigeria is not unachievable. First and foremost, any country can achieve peace in large measure by implementing sound government. There shouldn't be any insecurity for all Nigerians, since the current upsurge is akin to a catastrophe; everyone is susceptible to its threat. Thus, it is the duty of all Nigerians (the ruling elite and their people) to combat insecurity in the country. This does not imply that every Nigerian should behave like an army or provide security; rather, it simply implies that everyone in Nigeria needs to be aware of their surroundings. To improve security, a range of contemporary formal and informal policing theories should be supported, including vigilantism, zero-tolerance policing, community policing (which entails a commitment from the police and the community), and intelligence-led policing. Sulaiman, (2024).

As stated under the rule of law, "nobody is above the law." There are claims that a few well-known Nigerian politicians are complicit in the actions of Boko Haram. The criminal judicial system will look into and confirm the claims, after which one of the primary objectives of Boko Haram is to stop impunity by prosecuting the police officials who are suspected of killing

Mohammed Yusuf outside of court. to look into and prosecute crimes that are allegedly perpetrated by the Federal, State, and Local Governments must prioritize maintaining national security by increasing their expenditures on intelligence and surveillance Abalaka, (2023). To achieve security in Nigeria, government representatives, business-people, and state security agencies will all be involved and diligent in their efforts.

Becoming brothers' keepers through unity is another action that will benefit Nigerians in this time of insecurity. Obafemi Awolowo (2020), a Nigerian patriot, famously remarked, "We must labor so that our unity may endure Following "goals and ideals that are noble, elevating, and capable of benefiting the vast majority of our people," the late Sir Ahmadu Bello, the first premier of Nigeria, proposed that "burying our differences and that the correct approach is not to try to bury our differences but understand those differences" as a solution to the country's problems of disunity (quoted in Mgbeke, 2019:11).

Assist political, traditional, and religious authorities in the north in disarming, radicalizing, and reintegrating Islamist terrorists; carry on constructing regional security links and networks on a bilateral and international scale; To stop armed organizations and criminals from moving freely across borders and causing significant harm to adjacent nations, Nigeria's international allies should step up combined patrols at Nigeria's borders such as Cameroon and Niger; communicate and exchange intelligence data more frequently. Additionally, those who belong to Boko Haram and other terrorist groups who feel that they have not received justice should know that they are a part of the solution. For the sake of the survival of the nation, the innocent citizens, and their families, they must accept a peaceful resolution Sulaiman, (2024).

Ineffective leadership

In business and government, poor decision-making practices are referred to as bad governance. It is also completely at odds with effective leadership. Irregular policy making, deceit by the governed, systematic corruption, and a lack of transparency and accountability are all characteristics of bad governance Sulaiman, (2024).

Poor governance, according to the World Bank, is when a nation has "any if the readings of every indicator are near to or less than -2.5. The World Bank's governance indices are as follows:

1. Speak up and take responsibility
2. Lawfulness
3. Regulatory excellence
4. Prevention of corruption
5. Efficiency of government

Reasons For Poor Leadership

a. Absence of voice and accountability

When governing bodies disregard the opinions of the people they are in charge of and are unable to accept accountability for their actions, bad governance is the result. The governing body no longer hears or takes into consideration the opinions of head people when they are disregarded. Democratic administrations place a strong emphasis on accountability to make sure the general public is informed about events and knows what to do if something goes wrong. In turn, mistrust between the two sides is bred by a lack of accountability, which results in instability. Due to uncertainty and doubt, there is an unfavorable connection between the parties Ajiteru, (2021) .

b. Underdevelopment of politics

Political power has been shaped in the framework of the global economic and political systems through interactions with the wealthier "core" countries, which are primarily responsible for the political underdevelopment that permeates the majority of the "South." State leaders' underdependence on the people is a major contributing factor to political underdevelopment. Poor

nations are comparable to each other when it comes to formal organizational characteristics. The main cause of the large variations in state-society relationship patterns is the difference in state functioning.

C. Corruption

It's common knowledge that poor governance and corruption go hand in hand. Corruption can occur in a variety of contexts, including the political and business spheres. Corrosion can happen in various ways. When there is a crime within a governing body, officials prioritize themselves over the interests of others, which results in poor governance Sulaiman, (2024).

Crime affects law enforcement agencies like the police as well as social services like health and education in developing nations.

Consequences of Incompetent Leadership

The effects of poor governance are far-reaching and do not stop at the circumstances in which it takes place:

- i. not working state
- ii. inadequate expansion of the economy
- iii. Corruption
- iv. Instances of inadequate governance

Examples of poor governance

The examples that follow are by no means all-inclusive. The standards are arranged in opposition to suggestions under the five categories of good practice listed in the Good Practice Guide for Governing Bodies Ajiteru,(2021).

<p>Primary Accountabilities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ There is no strategic plan or proof that a strategic plan has any effect ➤ There is no evidence that the institution or its students are ambitious. ➤ There is no plan to ensure financial stability or a positive reputation. ➤ There is no indication of proper monitoring or financial controls or taking prompt, effective action when others discover failures or wrongdoings
<p>Critical attributes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Recruitment practices to the governing body are an opaque or 'old boy', resulting in a talent or experience basis that is insufficient ➤ The Chair or other members of the governing body are not visible, causing their positions to be misunderstood ➤ Too much involvement by members of the governing body in the institution leads to a lack of understanding of the institution’s mission and ‘business’
<p>Openness and transparency</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ There is no yearly report on institutional performance written and distributed both within and outside the organization ➤ There is no publicly accessible registration of the interests of members of the governing body ➤ Staff and students are not given access to the governing body’s proceedings and judgments ➤ The university does not provide specific information on its student acceptance standards and processes on its website

Examining:

Significant violence has resulted from the widespread rallies in Nigeria against poor governance and economic hardship Abalaka, (2023). The effects of rising costs of living on people's

livelihoods have not been lessened by government solutions to the economic problems that communities face. Potential threats to national stability are posed by the civil protests, which are a reflection of growing tensions, widespread dissatisfaction, and a collapsing social compact between the state and its people. But the government's reaction, which included using force and cracking down on nonviolent protestors, goes against fundamental democratic values like the freedom of speech and the right to peaceful assembly. Democracy depends on these fundamental rights because they allow people to hold elected officials responsible for their deeds.

The demonstrations have revealed long-standing problems and had a significant social and economic impact on the nation. In addition to causing significant property damage and disrupting educational and economic activity, the violence and unrest that have been linked to the situation have raised worries about public safety, especially in locations where key roadways and commercial centers have been damaged or blocked. For example, trade and transportation have been negatively impacted by the blockade of the Abuja-Kaduna route in Suleja and the burning of automobiles along the Abuja-Keffi highway in Nasarawa State Abalaka, (2023).

The federal government, several civic organizations, state governors from a range of political backgrounds, opinion leaders, and traditional leaders have all taken proactive steps to try and defuse the unrest, but the protests have persisted and in some cases have turned violent across the state lines. They weaken public confidence in institutions, violate basic democratic rights, draw criticism from across the globe, and impede the supremacy of law. Maintaining democratic ideals and promoting a stable and just society depends on addressing these abuses and guaranteeing respect for human rights Sulaiman, (2024).

There is variation in the responses around the nation to these protests. Many officials in the northern regions have endorsed the protests, seeing in them a call for necessary reforms as well as a manifestation of deep-seated national discontent. They saw the protests as an acceptable means of expressing public disapproval of the structural problems afflicting the country.

By contrast, youth groups in the Niger Delta region have shown greater skepticism. They have questioned the reasons for the protests, speculating that they might be influenced by other factors or that they might not adequately address the particular issues of their area Sulaiman, (2024).

This regional discrepancy highlights the protests' complexity and multifaceted character and reveals differing opinions about their legitimacy and objectives throughout Nigeria Ajiteru,(2021).

Many Nigerians are worried that the protests won't offer a long-term solution to the country's problems with terrible governance, food inflation, and economic hardship. These worries stem from the broad agitation demanding an end to these problems. Rather, there is concern that the disturbances may present chances for criminal groups to take advantage of the circumstances. However, several organizations have expressed their support for the ongoing economic reforms and palliatives that the federal government has started in each of the 36 states Sulaiman, (2024).

The demonstrations have greatly alarmed the populace, especially in states like Kano, Jigawa, Niger, Nasarawa, Borno, and Yobe where violent incidents and explosions have occurred of IEDs planted by alleged Boko Haram terrorists, as well as unlawful acts carried out by gangs of thugs who sought to take control of the demonstrations and destroy vital infrastructure and properties across the states. The government had to endeavor to mitigate the prevailing turmoil, tackle the underlying reasons behind the demonstrations, and reestablish stability and confidence within the nation Abalaka, (2023).

Solutions to Bad Governance

- a. Transparency
- b. Candidates for public office must declare all of their assets and income.
- c. application of the research conducted by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) on the standards and code framework

- d. All papers about legislation and parliamentary voting, as well as any political contributions made to political parties, must be made public.
- e. Laws about governing domains, including business, politics, and so forth, are distinct.

Dealing with corruption

- I. New organizations and legislation are shown
- ii. Targeting vulnerable services is important.
- iii. Community-based change services
- iv. Legislation that facilitates the collection of bribes ought to be removed.
- V. Increase the amount of objective criteria used to decide if a service qualifies for reimbursement.
- Vi. Use computers to communicate with government officials less frequently.

Intervention Mechanisms:

1. To prevent additional breakdowns in peace and security, the states of Borno, Yobe, Nasarawa, Kano, Katsina, and Jigawa implemented curfews on August 1, 2024.
2. The Federal Government has delivered 740 bags of rice to all 36 states and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) to alleviate the consequences of food inflation and economic hardship, with a focus on the most vulnerable segments of society.
3. July 29, 2024: The President's administration are shown Targeting vulnerable services is important.
4. Community-based change services Legislation that facilitates the collection of bribes ought to be removed.
5. Increase the amount of objective criteria used to decide if a service qualifies for reimbursement.
6. Use computers to communicate with government officials less frequently.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Proactive action by the federal government is necessary to reduce hostilities and deal with the underlying problems. establishing communication with protest organizers and offering guarantees to allay their worries.
2. To safeguard vital infrastructure, guarantee public safety, and stop criminal elements from taking advantage of protests, the federal and state governments should increase security and public safety by sending out more staff.
3. The federal and state governments should start and support initiatives to strengthen government responsiveness to citizen needs, boost transparency, and improve governance. Local authorities should also support these initiatives Ajiteru,(2021).
4. To promote community engagement projects that aim to establish mutual trust and understanding between citizens and government institutions, the Federal and State governments ought to work in conjunction with traditional rulers and community leaders Sulaiman, (2024).

In Summary

This research explores the relationship between insurgencies and other forms of insecurity in Nigeria and poor leadership. But the nation's vulnerability shouldn't be attributed to poor leadership alone. The dynamic of the interaction between the ruled and the ruler Making decisions is a bad kind of government. Poor governance can be attributed to a variety of factors, including both external and internal problems with the ruling class. Unfair policy implementation, deceit, and corruption are a few instances of bad governance Sulaiman, (2024). A failed state, slow economic growth, and a rise in corruption are the results of bad governance. Improving decision-making transparency and combating corruption are the two main ways to address poor

governance. Additional elements that appear to presuppose intervening variables (such as religious extremism and/or youth indoctrination with harmful ideas, ethnicity, and unity issues) can also be linked to these two main causes. These factors also provide room for further issues to arise. Nigerians must band together to combat this threat, and their leaders must pledge to act in the best interests of the greatest number of people. The Middle Belt has long been plagued by inter communal conflicts; the emergence of the Bakassi Boys, MOSOP, MEND, OPC, MASSOB, and the extremist theological views of Boko-Haram are all signs that something is amiss Sulaiman, (2024).

REFERENCES

1. Abalaka, J.N,(2023). Youth's Unemployment and Crime in Nigeria: A Nexus and Implication for Development. *International Journal of Sociology and Anthropology*. 5 (8): 350-357.
2. Ajaegbu, O.O. (2022). Rising Youth Unemployment and Violent Crimes in Nigeria. *American Journal of Social Issues and Humanities*. 2(5) 315-321.
3. Ajiteru, S.A.R, (2021). *Justice For All (J4A)* Newsletter.
4. Akwara, A.F., Akwara, N.F., Enwuchola, A., Adekunle, M., Udaw, J.E. (2023). Unemployment and Poverty: Implications for National Security and Good Governance in Nigeria. *International Journal of Public Administration and Management Research*. 2 (1).
5. Bellamy, AJ. and Wheeler, NJ. (2024). "Humanitarian Interventions in World Politics". In Baylis, J., Smith, S. & Owens, P. (eds.) *The Globalization of World Politics*: (4th Ed.) Oxford: Oxford University Press.
6. Baylis, J. (2008). "International and Global Security." In Baylis, J., Smith, S. & Owens, P. (eds.) *The Globalization of World Politics*: (4th Ed.) Oxford: Oxford University Press.
7. Brown, C. (2024). "Human Rights". In Baylis, J., Smith, S. & Owens, P. (eds) (2008) *The Globalization of World Politics*: (4th Ed.) Oxford: Oxford University Press.
8. *Council on Foreign Relations* (2014) www.dailytrust.com.ng (Retrieved on 9th February, 2015).
9. Currie, E. (2015). The Politics of Crime: The American Experience', in Stenson, K. and Cowell, D. (eds), *The Politics of Crime Control*. London: Sage.
10. Dambazau, A.(2021). *Criminology and Criminal Justice*. Lagos: Spectrum Books.
11. Gandu, Y.K. (2022). Terrorism in Social History and the Capitalist Mode of Production. *Bayero Sociologist, A Journal of Sociological Studies*. 1(3) 45-66.
12. Igabatayo, S.A. (2018) Towards Good Governance and Political Pluralism in Nigeria: The from Military Dictatorship to Democratic Rule. *In Journal of Arts and Social Sciences*, Igbinedion University, Okada, p. 2434.
13. International Crisis Group (2014). *Curbing Violence in Nigeria (II) The 'Boko Haram' Insurgence*. *Africa Report*. Brussels, Belgium No.216 3th April, 2014. Brussels@crisisgroup.org
14. Lee, D., and Newby, (2015). *The Problem of Sociology: An Introduction to the Discipline*. London: Routledge.
15. Macionis, J.J. (2019). *Social Problems*. Belmont: Pearson/Prentice-Hall.
16. Mukhtar, J. I., Mohammed, S. I. & Sani, I. (2016). Poverty, Unemployment and the Challenges of Security in Nigeria-The Nexus. *Journal of Political Inquiry*, 2 (1): 232 244
17. Naidoo, S. (n.d.) *A Theoretical Conceptualization of Human Security: Institute of Global Dialogue*, Johannesburg.
18. Nyong, M.O. (2023). *Unemployment Convergence among the 36 States in Nigeria*. Being a Revised Paper Presented at Finance and Economic Conference in Frankfurt Am Main, Germany, Thursday 4th July-Saturday 6th July, 2023.

19. Obiozor, G. (2022). *Uneasy Friendship: Nigeria/ US Relations*. Enugu: Fourth Dimension Publishers.
20. Ogbeyi, M.M. (2022). Political Leadership and Corruption in Nigeria since 1960. *Journal of Nigeria Studies* Vol. 1 No. 2, Fall 2012.
21. Ogunleye, G.O. Adewale, O.S., Alese, B.K., and Ogunde, B.A. (2021). A Computer-Based Security Framework for Crime Prevention in Nigeria. *Information Technology for People Centered Development* by Nigeria Computer Society, 10th International Conference, July 25-29, 2011.
22. Omede, J. (2022). Youth Unrest and Vices in Nigeria: Values and Moral Education as Possible Panaceas. *Research Journal in Organizational Psychological and Educational Studies*. 1 (6) 313-318.
23. Omotor, IG (2019). Socio-economic Determinants of Crime in Nigeria. *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences*. 6 (2) 54-59.
24. Persson, H. (2014). Nigeria-An Overview of Challenges to Peace and Security. FOI, February, 2014.
25. Pojman, L.p (2023). *Global Political Philosophy*: Boston, McGrawHill.
26. Radda, S.I. (2024). Towards Optimum Resource Management by Governments. *NSASA Journal, 2007/2008*, p. 6-14.
27. Radda, S.I. (2022). Assessment of the Activities of the EFCC in the Fight Against Corruption in Nigeria. *Bayero Sociologist, A Journal of Sociological Studies*. 1(3): 31- 44.
28. Radda, S.I. & Dumbulun, K.B. (2021). A Discourse on the Causes and Consequences of Armed Robbery on Nigeria. *The Bayero Sociologist, A Journal of Sociological Studies*, Maiden Edition. Pp. 152-167.
29. Robert-Okah, A. (2018) Strategies for Security Management in Nigeria: A Roadmap For Peace and National Security. *An International Multidisciplinary Journal, Ethiopia*, 8 (3) 1-17.
30. Simonis, U.E. (Ed.) (2018). *Defining Good Governance-Conceptual Competition is on*. Berlin: Open Access Repository.
31. Sulaiman, T.H (2024). *How Bad Governance Impedes Poverty Alleviation in Bangladesh*. Working Paper No. 147. Research Program on: Good Governance and Poverty Alleviation. OECD Development Center.
32. The Free Dictionary.com (2014). Foreign Assistance. In Farlex, inc. Ujo, A. A. (2018). *Theory and Practice of Development Administration*. Kaduna: Joyce Graphic Printers.
33. Ulu, J. (2019). *Fight Against Corruption: Rule of Law will Succeed*. Abuja: New Jerusalem Books.
34. United States Agency for International Development (2016). www.google.com (Retrieved on 20th November, 2014).